

Prototype for data and Knowledge Exploration Tool

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1. Contents

2. Summary	4
3. Introduction	4
4. Exploration Tool Prototype	5
4.1 Conceptual Overview.....	6
4.2 Core Functionalities	7
4.3 Prototype Design of the Exploration Tool.....	8
5. Semantic Knowledge Tool Prototype	18
5.1 Conceptual Overview of the Knowledge Semantic Tool - PERSEUS	18
5.2 Privacy and Data Requirements.....	18
6. Future Strategies.....	21
6.1 Checklist for toolbox final version development	21
6.2 Integration with EHEN toolbox platform	22
6.3 Possible Future Implementation.....	22
7. References	23
8. Annex 1.	24
9. Annex 2.	25
9.1 The technology stack for the Exploration Tool	25
9.2 The technology stack for the Knowledge semantic tool.	26

2. Summary

The Equal-Life project aims to investigate the combined effects of various exposures on children and adolescent mental health and cognitive development across life course. Important to this project is the development of an interactive web platform, referred to as the Equal-Life toolbox. The Equal-Life toolbox is a content-rich platform that supports the exploration and the organization of complex data to advance understanding of the exposome's role in mental health change during childhood and adolescence. While still evolving and somewhat abstract outside academic circles, the exposome concept is critical to this endeavor. The toolbox aims to clarify the relationships between diverse results, tools, and definitions constituting the exposome's impact on young mental health. It serves as a guide, helping users to synthesize information and understand how interconnected research areas create a holistic view of the exposome, transcending domain-specific perspectives.

This deliverable describes the prototype of the Equal-Life toolbox. We offer a comprehensive description of the two primary tools that underlie the exploratory functions of the toolbox: the exploratory tool and the semantic knowledge tool.

These tools are designed to delve into the metadata and results of the H2020 project Equal-Life (<https://www.equal-life.eu/en>) as described by van Kamp et al. 2022, to facilitate the exploration of the results of the project, in terms of metadata, documents, models, protocols, and codes.

This prototype and its functionalities have been refined through feedback from internal and external stakeholder workshops (<https://www.equal-life.eu/en/documenten/d81>), ensuring the toolbox is as user-centric and effective as possible.

3. Introduction

The Equal-Life data environment is a complex and multilayered system where outcomes of highly diverse research intersect. It aims to describe the patterns among different factors (exposures) and children and adolescents' mental health and cognitive development. This interdisciplinary nature makes the research comprehensive from a scientific perspective yet challenging to explore and transfer. This pertains to both quantitative data (data sets, aggregated data and results), referring to the numeric results expected from cohort and in-depth study data analyses, and qualitative output, encompassing scientific publications, statistical codes deliverables, and future guidelines that are currently being produced and will continue to be developed until the project's completion.

Data accessibility came forward as a critical challenge in a project like Equal-Life. From the outset, the task of the toolbox development was complex as it focused on making the project's outputs accessible. Based on the feedback gathered from various meetings with stakeholders

and internal project partners, a prototype primarily centered around accessibility was developed.

In this deliverable, we present the Exploratory Tool and the Knowledge Semantic tool prototyped as a dynamic web page designed to facilitate interaction with the project's contents. The Exploratory Tool is an interactive gateway to the project's extensive outcomes, where content is structured to ensure that access to all the contents is facilitated by a multiple access strategy (For a more comprehensive description of the exploratory tool and a detailed contents structure in the exploratory tools see in the following sections).

The Exploratory Tool in our prototype is supported by a Semantic Knowledge Tool, which adds a layer of sophistication to the exploration process. The Semantic Knowledge Tool empowers users to engage in semantic searches, allowing for nuanced and context-aware data retrieval, thus facilitating the overall user experience.

The exploration tools (integrated with the knowledge semantic tool) can be reached from the official Equal-Life toolbox page at the following address: <https://www.equal-life.eu/en/toolbox>.

An interim domain is currently in use to host the prototype as described in section 4.1

Furthermore, the project team is actively refining and implementing advanced features, like more interactive data visualization and exploration, which will be fine-tuned based on incoming project outputs. These features will enhance the user experience and the depth of exploration, making the tool even more effective and user centered. The aim is to provide a comprehensive platform that houses a multi-layer source of information, empowers users to extract meaningful insights and explore the intricate connections between various factors and children/adolescents' mental health and cognitive development.

The prototype is intended to be further developed. As such, it will undergo changes based on the outcomes and feedback that will be collected in the coming months, both externally and internally, from the project. Regardless, one of the purposes of this document is to define the structure on which the future development of the two presented tools will be based. [OBJ]

4. Exploration Tool Prototype

With many indicators of exposure, outcomes and mediators, and a whole range of publications, background documents, protocols, data, and codes, it is crucial to have an exploration tool that can assist researchers and stakeholders in navigating through various information and content. for the development of this toolbox in Equal-Life, we adopted a co-design approach, placing a strong emphasis on communication and involvement with stakeholders from the very first steps of the project (see deliverable 8.3) This chapter presents the conceptualization of the exploration tool, specifically how topics, links, materials, and other available information will be made accessible to users to create content exploration as easily as possible.

4.1 Conceptual Overview

The Exploration Tool is a visual platform specially designed to help researchers and stakeholders (A description of different stakeholders involved in the project is available in the deliverable 8.3 and D10.3), to assess and understand various exposure factors. Based on the 'exposome' concept, this tool employs data visualisation techniques to facilitate the representation and interpretation of information organized in multiple layers. Each layer provides a different perspective or level of detail. By leveraging innovative visualisation technologies, the Exploration Tool aims to enable users to explore patterns within the Equal-life results.

The expected results of this project are summarised in Annex 1.

In summary, the types of results are:

Texts: deliverables, publications, guidelines, and any writing produced to inform and disseminate.

Protocols: protocols were produced in the experimental phases for harmonising data, submitting interviews, conducting data collection, definition documents (see for more details D9.5) etc.

Aggregate statistics: from the analysis of the data cohorts, various descriptive statistics were obtained for the various indicators, mediators, and outcomes taken into analysis.

Tools: software and libraries were produced in the research area to support the analysis and collection of data used within the project. These objects are available in different programming languages and modes (Python, R, command line, etc.).

Models: conceptual model for exposome, mediators and outcome; the conceptual framework for the social exposome; logic model for equity impact assessment.

The concept for our tool draws clear inspiration from the framework Google has established for employing AI-related ideas. We intend to empower users to navigate the content along a self-directed path rather than constraining them to a predefined narrative flow. At any entry point (elaborated upon in the subsequent paragraphs), the user can link to other related elements within the tool, with these connections formed as outcomes are identified and integrated into the toolbox. A dedicated editorial board has been formed to assess the content and decide its application.

The Equal-Life handbook (here referred to as a guidebook) provides guidance to use the tools. It is incorporated as an interactive object accessible from the website and serves as the cornerstone for organizing the content. (add task and deliverable nr)

The toolbox prototype is currently hosted on page:

<https://quantacons.editorx.io/elatlans>

Takeaway: Exploration Tool turns complex exposure/outcome/mediation data into precise, interactive visual representations, empowering users to identify patterns, make comparisons, and extract meaningful insights that further the field of exposome science applied to children and adolescent mental health.

4.2 Core Functionalities

The prototype design of the Exploration Tool has been conceived with user-friendliness, efficient data representation, and interactive functionalities in mind. The prototype of the Exploration Tool is not just a product of technical expertise and advanced programming but also a demonstration to the collaborative effort between our team and various stakeholders as potential users. The co-design process was pivotal in shaping the tool's functionalities, usability, and overall design. We engaged with researchers, data analysts, health professionals, and community representatives to understand their needs and perspectives. Through consultations, workshops, and feedback sessions, we collaboratively refined the prototype design to ensure its user-friendly practicality and to serve a broad range of use cases. This diverse input pool has been instrumental in guiding the development process, providing the tool is robust, intuitive, and capable of meeting the complex demands of exposure data analysis. Therefore, The Exploration Tool is a product of collective intelligence and shared vision, making it an analytical platform and a collaborative virtual environment.

The Exploration Tool offers a suite of robust functionalities that cater to the needs of researchers and stakeholders involved in studying exposure factors. Its core functionalities are:

Interplay Outcomes Visualization: This core functionality allows for dynamic and interactive visualizations of multi-dimensional outcomes from the project. Users can easily navigate complex information that might otherwise be difficult to explore.

This functionality enables users to explore and visualize the interplay between different exposure variables and the effect of accumulation of exposures in specific environments.

Tools Gallery: A suite of tools and functionalities available to the user within the platform. It is designed to showcase different features and capabilities that users can leverage to perform specific tasks. In particular, the different tools developed within the project will be displayed.

Concept exploration: The most promising and key role concepts will be summarized and made dynamically explorable and searchable.

Reference ontology: A reference ontology promotes standardisation by providing a set of agreed-upon terms and concepts, making it easier for various systems and organisations to interact because they are "speaking the same language". This step makes exploring content

more usable and understandable. The definitions result from research conducted during Equal-Life by domain experts qualified for such discussion.

Meeting point: The idea is to make the platform more than a one-way tool with an asset stakeholder project. Thanks to the invaluable input from the stakeholders who participated in the project and the discussion tables, the toolbox wants to create a two-way connection where stakeholders will contribute with their testimonies and provide their experiences.

The tool was designed to be implemented in the final version with future research needs in mind. The tool is scalable and adaptable, permitting the addition of new functionalities and capabilities as required.

4.3 Prototype Design of the Exploration Tool

To improve the accessibility of the content, we decided to structure the main page so that access would be redundant. It will be possible to access the same content through different links. This is because, after internal and stakeholder discussions, we realized that in a project like Equal-Life, many stakeholders have different needs in accessing information (see Figure 1). In D9.1, we assumed three macro-categories of stakeholders (researcher, specialist, and policy maker). After four years of the project, we remain convinced that the subdivision into macro-categories remains valid but is limiting in some aspects, such as the prediction of an information pathway, as these macro-categories do not determine the content of interest. For this reason, we structured the main page and the menus of the other pages so that the contents would be as interconnected as possible and navigable from different points. How these contents will be structured is described in detail in the following chapter.

Figure 1 : The figure shows the map of close to Equal-Life project’s stakeholdes distribution in Europe and their different backgrounds. The data refer to preliminary, unpublished results of interviews conducted within the framework of WP8 activities to increase knowledge of the needs and opinions of

stakeholders regarding the concept of the exposome about the mental health of children and adolescents.

4.3.1 Design Components

The user interface (UI) of the Exploration tool, developed with Editor X (<https://www.editorx.com/>) for website development, is designed to be aesthetically pleasing, intuitive, and easy to navigate, ensuring an optimal user experience while handling complex exposure data. The central diagram of the components is shown in Figure 2. A detailed explanation of each component is to follow in the text.

Figure 2: The main schema of prototype resources structure where **A** is the home page, **B** are the three main components related to the Project results: Tools-Guidebook-Explorable and **C** are the three components related to dissemination: Training - Research – Network.

4.3.1.1 A - Homepage

The homepage serves as the gateway to the exploration tool. It briefly introduces the tool, its purpose, and its functionalities.

The page includes information about the project's partners, cohorts, stakeholders, publications, in-depth studies, and supported interventions.

The page's contents are organized in a single column with headings and subheadings, and the information is presented in a concise and easy-to-read format.

Equal-Life Toolbox

With the Equal-Life Project, we are pioneering a holistic approach to child well-being, integrating advanced technology, data analysis, and the exposome to pave the way for a brighter future where every child can flourish.

Join us on this transformative journey towards equal opportunities and a better life for our youngest generation

Figure 3 shows the screenshot of the open view in the web version.

The user is presented with a brief description of the toolbox and a choice of three macro topics: **Tools - Guidebook - Explorable** (For more detailed information, see next paragraph)

The three buttons connect to the three respective pages. The division was based on internal discussions concerning the project outcomes and summarized in D10.5.

The term “Explorable” is under definition.

Following the idea of 'multi-access' to information, the home page was designed to allow information to be explored from different aspects. In addition to the three buttons representing the main access, two further access sections follow (see Figure 4):

- The section with the representative numbers of the project, called **Numerics**.

Numerics: key descriptive statistics about the project will be displayed. These numbers will be linked to pages with more information. For example, the number of partners will be connected to a page that lists Equal-Life partners (See Figure 4 . 2).

- The Menu gallery section called **Detailed Menu Gallery**

Detailed Menu Gallery: The user will be able to read a short description of the components before choosing how to navigate the site (See Figure 4 . 3)

Figure 4: The three main sections of the Home page: **1** primary access; **2** Numerics; **3** Detailed Menu Gallery.

4.3.1.2 B - Project Results Components

Tools:

The tools page is intended to be a gallery showing the different tools of Equal Life.

The page briefly describes the tools developed in equal-Life and available to the user. Each tool or collection of tools (should more than one have been developed within a given context) will have a brief description inside a box from which it will be possible to access a dedicated page.

There are no plans for the Equal-life team of developers to integrate the individual tools into the platform. The idea is to provide a detailed description of the tool developed and the necessary links. In the example shown in Figure 5, we reported the page dedicated to the tools developed within the framework of WP5. All tools remain hosted by the original platform of TUD, which is responsible for the development. Within the toolbox page, tutorials will be

available for using these tools in the context of studies focusing on Equal-Life. It will also be possible through the page to contact those responsible for future clarifications.

To make the search of the different tools available more efficient, it will be possible to search by keywords.

Each tool will be linked to the project outcomes whose achievement is connected to the development of the tools presented. Therefore, a link between the contents displayed in the guidebook and the tool descriptions in the gallery will be introduced.

Figure 5 Tools main page

Guidebook:

The page titled "Our Guidebook" introduces the Equal-Life Guidebook, which is described as a compilation of methods, best practices, and real-world examples for understanding and addressing the impact of the exposome on children and adolescent mental health and cognitive development. It explains that the recommendations within the guidebook are founded on data and insights from professionals in the field and academic research involved in the project. In particular, the content that will be featured in the guidebook comes from the publications produced during the project and that have undergone a rigorous review process both internal and external to the project.

The form in which the content will be displayed is inspired by the strategy used by Google in explaining what artificial intelligence is (<https://pair.withgoogle.com/>).

It was decided to use this information structure, having felt that the concept of exposome is very similar in complexity to that of AI. Moreover, structuring information allows for a reading that ranges from a synthetic to a highly detailed level. That multilayer approach fits very well with the diversity of users approaching the problem. Figure 6 shows how divided the page relates to the guidebook:

- A section titled "Start here" contains design patterns highlighting critical considerations for addressing the impact of the exposome on children's mental health and cognitive development.
- To help navigate through the guidebook's content, there are interactive elements, such as "Explore patterns" and filters by guiding questions.
- In the "Go deeper" section, chapters are based on documents written since 2020 for the project, which are periodically updated with new findings.

Figure 6 Guidebook main page

Figure 7 illustrates a structured, multi-layered approach to inquiry and research, beginning with a broad question setting the exploration stage.

It emphasizes how a wide-ranging question can guide the exploration of intricate connections within a topic. This question leads to identifying patterns representing segments of the answer, steering the user towards relevant information material and tools and promoting action-oriented strategies. At the core of this process lies a structured collection of information, which is pivotal for understanding the exposome's relation to the topic. It encourages users to delve into the content and is designed to incite tangible actions. The final layer of the model focuses on 'Information Tools,' which offer practical suggestions of tools, provide essential background descriptions, and present the results from analysis. This model is beneficial in fields where complex, interconnected systems impact outcomes, such as environmental health studies where the exposome—the totality of environmental exposures—plays a crucial role. The flowchart effectively encapsulates a dynamic framework for tackling comprehensive questions through a systematic and action-driven methodology.

Figure 7 Main schema of contents structure

Explorables:

The Exposome Data and Concepts page is designed to help the user navigate the qualitative and quantitative results of the project through different interactive objects.

The main page introduces the significance of the exposome's impact on children's mental health and cognitive development. It poses complex questions regarding determining environmental factors affecting mental well-being, the correlation between specific exposures and mental health outcomes and cognitive development, and the implications of collecting extensive data on children's environmental exposures.

Conceptual Models, Outcomes, Glossary: Three sections subdividing the exploration of contents based on different tools.

Conceptual Models: Encourages exploring how different variables and exposures can impact children's mental health and cognitive development, with a link to 'explore'. The idea, still being defined, is to make the different concept models developed in the project accessible through interactive graphics. The concepts will be linked to the guidebook's explanations and the glossary definitions.

Outcomes: Offers access to research results regarding the effects of the environment on children, also with an 'explore' link.

The dashboards will be the heart of the tool. Powered by Dash, they will provide an array of dynamic and interactive visualisations of exposure data. The dashboards comprise multiple panels, each dedicated to a specific aspect of the data.

In Figure 8, we show an example of content structure. For the mental health outcomes, it will be possible to explore different types of subjects like ADHD. Aggregate statistics from the project model results will be available for interactive exploration sessions.

Glossary: Provides access to the terminology for the main concepts discussed throughout the website.

A highlighted section is dedicated to explaining terms used throughout the site. It includes a search bar with colourful dots below it, suggesting an interactive element to aid in understanding the vocabulary.

Explorables

Figure 8: the Figure show the structure of Explorables main page as described in the main text. From the gallery menu (2) it'll be possible explore the : Conceptual models (5); The outcomes (3) and the Glossary(4).

5. Semantic Knowledge Tool Prototype

5.1 Conceptual Overview of the Knowledge Semantic Tool - PERSEUS

In the context of Equal Life, we decided to integrate PERSEUS – Public Engagement for Responsive and Shared European Union Strategies. PERSEUS (<https://perseus-platform.eu/>), represents a key instrument for extracting and harnessing knowledge from an array of data-rich sources, thereby offering comprehensive, evidence-based insights to guide decision-making processes.

Rooted in an ontology that models complex variables and relationships, PERSEUS supports a holistic exploration of the "external exposome", the totality of environmental exposures from conception onwards. Its ontology encapsulates the vastness of ecological, social, and individual-level exposures, capturing the intricate interplay between these factors.

Simultaneously, PERSEUS can help to recognize the importance of time activity patterns and the specific relevance of exposure effects across different life stages. It enables researchers to track single versus accumulated indicators and examine the differential exposure to negative and positive environmental characteristics, acknowledging the significance of differential vulnerability or resilience.

In summary, PERSEUS, within the Equal-Life context, provides a platform for an in-depth exploration of the external exposome, balancing the intricate demands of scientific rigor, stakeholder input, and policy-making considerations. It, therefore, embodies a vital instrument in understanding the broader implications of environmental exposures and formulating effective, context-specific strategies to mitigate their impact.

PERSEUS will not be visible with a separate interface in the toolbox but will be the tool for connecting and searching for content on par with a search engine. It will then be possible for the end user to explore through semantic search the different contents. In addition, PERSEUS will be used for stable connections between different semantic objects such as definitions in the glossary.

5.2 Privacy and Data Requirements

5.2.1 Privacy Measures

To maintain user privacy and confidentiality, PERSEUS has been designed with a stringent data handling policy. Specifically, the platform does not store any of the content from the documents uploaded by its users. Instead, a user who uploads a document must provide a publicly accessible link to download the document. This feature not only upholds privacy standards but also minimises the storage demands on the platform. The primary purpose of document upload is

to facilitate the indexing of information within the platform's Data Index rather than retaining the document content.

5.2.2 Required Fields for Documents Upload

When a user uploads a document to PERSEUS, specific fields are mandatory to provide structured and searchable metadata associated with each record. These fields may vary depending on the resource type, but as of the current implementation, the following are required (the input graphical interface is shown in Figures 11 and 12):

Title: A descriptive name for the document.

Institution: The name of the institution or organisation associated with the record.

Authors: A list of authors associated with the record, separated by commas.

Publication Date: The date when the paper was published or made available.

Keywords: A list of significant words or phrases associated with the record, separated by commas.

Resource Type: The document type, which can be a research paper, deliverable, webpage, etc.

License: The licensing terms of the document, which could be Open Access or Private.

Download Link: A URL from where the document can be downloaded.

Document: The actual .pdf file of the document.

Description or Abstract: A summary or abstract of the document.

Other Resources: Any other URLs related to the document.

Knowledge Graph Classes: List of classes from the ontology that are relevant to the document.

The fields above are searchable, contributing to the platform's robust and effective data retrieval capabilities.

Figure 11: Document search page; the graphical interface of PERSEUS for a query search.

Upload Resource

Title*	<input type="text" value="Enter Title"/>
Institution*	<input type="text" value="Enter Institution"/>
Authors*	<input type="text" value="Enter the list of Authors as Name1 Surname"/>
Publication Date*	<input type="text" value="dd/mm/yyyy"/>
Keywords*	<input type="text" value="Enter Keywords as Keyword1, Keyword2, etc."/>
Components	<input type="checkbox"/> COCTEAU <input type="checkbox"/> AGGREGATOR <input type="checkbox"/> Foresight
Policy Sectors	<input type="checkbox"/> Technology <input type="checkbox"/> Data protection <input type="checkbox"/> Climate <input type="checkbox"/> Health <input type="checkbox"/> EU <input type="checkbox"/> International Governance
Resource Type	<input type="text" value="Document"/>
License	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Open Access <input type="radio"/> Private

Download Link*	<input type="text" value="Download Link"/>
Document File*	<input type="button" value="Choose file"/> No file chosen
Description (Abstract)*	<input type="text" value="Description or Abstract of the Document..."/>
Other Resources	<input type="text" value="Enter Other Resources"/>
knowledge Graph classes	<input type="button" value="Select"/>

I declare I am authorized to share the uploaded content.

Figure 12: Upload resources—the graphical interface of input request in PERSEUS. The page aims to collect the information needed to describe the uploaded document.

6. Future Strategies

6.1 Checklist for toolbox final version development

By focusing on the following strategies, the Equal-Life project can ensure that the toolbox remains a state-of-the-art resource, providing valuable insights into child-environment interactions' long-term effects on mental health and cognitive development.

- Engage with end-users, such as researchers, urban planners, public health officials, health care providers, and educators, to understand their needs and ensure the toolbox is user-friendly and meets practical requirements.
- Employ an agile development process with regular iterations and updates based on stakeholder feedback.
- Perform usability testing to refine the interface and improve the overall user experience.
- Continue to develop and integrate tools from various work packages into the toolbox.

- Ensure these tools are seamlessly connected and accessible via the Exploratory Tool.
- Plan to scale the toolbox to handle increasing data as the project progresses.
- Establish a maintenance and update plan for the toolbox, ensuring it remains up-to-date with the latest research findings and technologies.
- Publish findings and insights from the toolbox to scientific communities and the public.

In particular, the following future actions will be followed to promote a long-term maintenance strategy from a toolbox maintenance and optimization point of view:

Enhancing Data Accessibility and Management:

- Further development of methods for efficient data storage, retrieval, and sharing within the bounds of data protection regulations.

Training and Documentation:

- Create documentation and tutorials for the toolbox to facilitate its adoption.
- Conduct training sessions for potential users to ensure they can fully utilise the toolbox.
- Documentation on implemented training (tips, tricks and context) in one or several pilot studies for training.
- Develop an outreach strategy to increase the visibility and impact of the project.

Data Privacy and Security:

- Develop robust security protocols to protect sensitive data, especially considering child and adolescent data involvement.
- Ensure the toolbox complies with all relevant data protection laws, such as GDPR.

6.2 Integration with EHEN toolbox platform

As declared in the proposal, the toolbox's final version will be integrated into the EHEN toolbox web page and the Equal-Life official web page.

6.3 Possible Future Implementation

For the future, we see two areas of development that will be explored and, if necessary, implemented based on the available content:

Semantic Enhancement and AI Utilization:

Expand the capabilities of the Semantic Knowledge Tool to include more advanced natural language processing and machine learning features.

Customisation and Personalization:

Allow users to customise their experience with the toolbox, tailoring it to their specific research or practical needs. Develop personalisation algorithms to suggest relevant data or tools based on the user's past activity and interests.

7. References

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8. Annex 1.

Preliminary summary of expected results per WPs based on internal table in D10.5

WP		Results/outcomes
WP1	Mechanism	- Conceptual models
		- Collection of research questions
		- Reviews sleep, stress, coping, restoration
WP2	Internal Exposome	- Choice of biological samples
		- Validated biomarkers
WP3	External Exposome	- Acoustic conditions of “real-life” settings classrooms
		- Development and validation of traffic modelling
		- Built and natural environment metrics
		- innovative noise modelling
		- models for exposome
WP4	Social Exposome	- conceptual framework of social exposome
		- definition of settings
		- logic model for equity impact assessment
		- equity relevant community level indicators
WP5	Multimodal Exposome Data Collection and Enrichment	- equity impact assessment of policies
		- data collection and enrichment tool 1
		- data collection and enrichment tool 2
		- final requirements for multimodal exposome
		- methodology for integrating infrastructural IoT in noise exposure
WP6	Integrative Data Analysis and Modelling	- data collection and enrichment tool 3
		- model code for feature selection
		- model code for pathway analysis
WP7	Health Effect Analysis	- finalised cohorts (results in working groups internalizing/externalizing, diagnosis, wellbeing)
		- pooled results
		- overview cohorts and in-depth data
		- biomarker information
WP8	Stakeholder Involvement and Intervention Development	- strategies stakeholder identification, interaction, involvement
		- layman terms paper on exposome pathways towards health effects
		- Identification of existing interventions
WP9	Tools, Training, and Implementation	- mockup data and knowledge exploration tool / meta data
		- handbook

WP10	Management, Ethics and Dissemination	- overview publications + public deliverables
WP11	Cluster Activities	Collection of EHEN blogs/newsletters we can potentially share?
WP12	Ethics Requirement	

9. Annex 2.

This annex contains all the technical specifications of the prototype divided by tool.

9.1 The technology stack for the Exploration Tool

The technology stack for the Exploration Tool is carefully selected to provide an efficient, secure, and scalable solution capable of handling vast amounts of data while offering dynamic and interactive visualisations. Here's an outline of the technology stack:

Front-end Development

The Web Interface is the front-end layer that users interact with, which brings together the data visualisations and allows for interactive research:

HTML/CSS/JavaScript to create the web pages and styles

Web Components for encapsulating and reusing visual elements.

Editor X: A cloud-based web development platform that allows users to create HTML5 websites through drag-and-drop tools. It's used for designing and managing the user interface of the tool's website.

The prototype is currently hosted on page:

<https://quantiacons.editorx.io/elatlans>

Programming Language: Where it is deemed valid, dashboards for dynamic content exploration will be developed. The development of these objects was based on the Python 3 programming language and the use of standard libraries such as:

Plotly: Plotly is a versatile graphing library that enables the creation of interactive, publication-quality graphs and dashboards in Python, R, and JavaScript. It's widely used for compelling visualisations that can be embedded in web applications or displayed as standalone web pages.

Dash: An open-source Python framework used for building analytical web applications. Dash is ideal for building data visualisation apps with highly custom user interfaces in pure Python. It is used for creating interactive and dynamic dashboards.

Back-end Development

Most of the code developed for the toolbox structure will be stored in GitHub (<https://github.com/quantiaconsulting>). GitHub is a favoured platform for storing code in European projects due to its adeptness at supporting collaboration across borders, with features that cater to distributed teams. Its robust version control capabilities, provided by Git, enable meticulous tracking and management of code changes over time, a critical factor for projects with multiple contributors.

Moreover, GitHub’s vast developer community and transparent, open-source environment encourage broader participation and public accountability—critical aspects for many European initiatives. Integrated project management tools, comprehensive documentation options, efficient issue tracking, and advanced security features further enhance its suitability for complex projects. Additionally, GitHub’s compatibility with various compliance standards ensures that projects can meet regulatory requirements. At the same time, its cloud-based nature offers global accessibility—a must-have for the geographical diversity typical in European collaborations.

Mobile and tablet version

The prototype is currently only optimised in the desktop version. Once the complete structure has been validated, the mobile and tablet versions will be optimised.

Data Security Strategy

Ensuring the privacy and security of the data inputted into the tool is paramount. The tool has robust security features to protect data integrity and confidentiality.

JWT (JSON Web Tokens): This securely transmits information between parties as a JSON object. JWT is used in authorisation and information exchange.

HTTPS/SSL: Secure protocols for safe data transfer over the network.

This technology stack ensures the Exploration Tool is high-performing, secure, and capable of handling the complex tasks necessary for exposure data visualisation and analysis.

9.2 The technology stack for the Knowledge semantic tool.

9.2.1 Overview

The architecture of the PERSEUS platform is built upon the Model-View-Controller (MVC) design pattern, a popular architectural pattern used in software engineering to separate the application logic into three interconnected components. This separation allows for efficient code organisation, modularity, and the concurrent development of the application.

9.2.2 Front-end

The Front End, or the 'View' in MVC, is what users interact with. In PERSEUS, the front end is implemented using a combination of HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, the fundamental technologies used to create and style the user interface of web applications. Thymeleaf, a Java-based library, is used for server-side rendering, allowing the creation of web views using HTML files that both developers and designers can understand. The Bootstrap Framework is used to design and customise responsive mobile-first sites, offering a variety of pre-made design templates for typography, forms, buttons, and other interface components.

9.2.3 Middle Tier

The Middle Tier, or the 'Controller' in MVC, handles the application's logic. It responds to user input, interacts with the data model, and selects which views to render. In PERSEUS, the middle tier is implemented in Java through Spring Boot. Spring Boot is an open-source Java-based framework used to create stand-alone, production-grade Spring-based Applications that can be started with minimal fuss. It includes embedded Tomcat, Jetty, or Undertow, so deploying WAR files is unnecessary.

9.2.4 Ontology

The Ontology, a vital part of the 'Model' in MVC, defines the data structure. In PERSEUS, the ontology is implemented using the Web Ontology Language (OWL), a semantic markup language for publishing and sharing data using ontologies on the Internet. The ontology can be accessed and downloaded from <https://periscope.lst.tfo.upm.es/>.

PERISCOPE is an ontology that models the policy decisions and the relative impact metrics during the pandemic. The ontology is implemented in OWL 2; its classes are organised in a hierarchical structure and annotated with their description.

Guidelines that will be followed during the ontology creation:

- The ontology will be created using Protégé (<https://protege.stanford.edu/>), a graphical tool for designing ontologies.
- Every term or keyword with a semantic relevance is a class
- Related terms will be grouped into superclasses
- The classes will be organised in a hierarchy or graph using relationships between types to deal with the semantic exploration of the documents.

9.2.5 Back-end

The Back End, also part of the 'Model' in MVC, handles data storage and retrieval. In PERSEUS, the back end comprises an Elasticsearch implementation with the User and Data Index. The User Index manages the users allowed to upload documents on the platform, while the Data Index organises the content and the descriptive fields of the documents uploaded. Documents are parsed and indexed by the PDF Processor, which collects the content from .pdf files. The User Script, an external Python script, creates and indexes new users.

The Figure show the main workflow of the knowledge semantic tool, explanations are present in the main text.

